

CHANGE MANAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE: A STUDY OF JUHEL PHARMACEUTICAL COMPANY AWKA ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: This study ascertained the effect of change management on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain; the effect of leadership change on employee performance; and change in organizational culture on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka. The sample size of 142 was determined using Taro Yamane Formula from a population of 221. Data were collected using structured questionnaire administered to respondents. The hypotheses were tested using OLS Regression with the aid of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences. Findings revealed that leadership change has significant effect on employee performance, and change in organizational culture has no significant effect on employee performance. The study concluded that managing change effectively provide benefits that help organizations sustain competitive advantage in the changing world. The study recommended that there is need for the organizations to empower employee to become change agent for better employee performance. Also, managers should give consideration to organizational culture dynamics as an aspect of change management for various reasons, such as adapting to market changes, improving employee engagement, fostering innovation, or responding to external pressures.

Keywords: Change, management, Leadership change, Change in organizational culture and Employee performance

Introduction

Change initiatives often disrupt existing routines, workflows, and relationships within organizations triggering resistance, uncertainty, and anxiety among employees (Kotter & Schlesinger, 2008). Ineffective change management practices can exacerbate these challenges, leading to decreased morale, increased turnover rates, and diminished performance levels across the organization (Armenakis, Harris & Mossholder, 2007). Conversely, well-designed change management processes can mitigate resistance, build resilience, and foster a culture of adaptability and innovation among employees (Cameron & Green, 2015). By providing clarity of purpose, communicating openly and transparently, and involving employees in decision-making processes, organizations can cultivate a sense of ownership and commitment to change initiatives, thereby enhancing employee performance and organizational outcomes (Lines, 2005).

Change management represents a critical aspect of organizational dynamics, particularly in today's rapidly evolving business environment characterized by technological advancements, globalization, and shifting market dynamics. Organizations across various industries face continuous pressures to adapt to changes in their internal and external environments, ranging from mergers and acquisitions to technological innovations and regulatory reforms (Hayes, 2018). The success of organizational change initiatives hinges not only on effective planning and implementation strategies but also on the ability to engage and mobilize employees throughout the change process. Employee performance plays a pivotal role in driving organizational effectiveness, productivity, and competitiveness, making it essential for organizations to understand the factors that influence employee performance during times of change (Battilana & Casciaro, 2012).

Moreover, effective change management practices facilitate the alignment of individual goals and objectives with broader organizational goals, fostering a sense of purpose and direction among employees (Oreg, Vakola & Armenakis, 2018). Clear communication channels, regular feedback mechanisms, and opportunities for skill development and training empower employees to navigate change with confidence and resilience, enabling them to adapt to new roles, responsibilities, and ways of working (Anderson & Anderson, 2010). The impact of change management on employee performance is contingent upon various contextual factors, including organizational culture, leadership styles, and the nature and magnitude of the change itself (Balogun & Hailey, 2008). Transformational leadership, characterized by visionary leadership, inspirational communication, and supportive coaching, has been associated with positive employee outcomes and organizational performance during times of change (Bass & Riggio, 2006).

Furthermore, organizational culture plays a critical role in shaping employee attitudes and behaviors towards change. Cultures that prioritize innovation, collaboration, and continuous learning tend to exhibit higher levels of employee engagement and performance during change initiatives (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). The present study aims to contribute to this body of knowledge by investigating the influence of change management practices on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited. Drawing upon theoretical frameworks from organizational behavior, human resource management, and change management literature, this research seeks to explore the mechanisms through which change management processes impact employee attitudes, behaviors, and performance outcomes.

In an ideal organizational environment, change management serves as a catalyst for enhancing employee performance and organizational effectiveness. The ideal state envisions a culture where change is embraced as an opportunity for growth and adaptation rather than a disruption to the status quo. Change management practices are seamlessly integrated into the fabric of the organization, fostering open communication, transparency, and employee engagement throughout the change process. Employees are empowered with the necessary skills, resources, and support to navigate transitions effectively, adapt to new ways of working, and contribute meaningfully to organizational goals. In this scenario, change management becomes a strategic enabler of employee performance, driving innovation, fostering resilience, and enhancing overall organizational agility in response to evolving market dynamics.

However, the present state often reveals a different reality, characterized by challenges and obstacles that hinder the effective implementation of change management initiatives and undermine employee performance. Many organizations struggle to effectively communicate the rationale behind changes, leading to resistance, uncertainty, and disengagement among employees. Additionally, inadequate planning, poor stakeholder engagement, and a lack of leadership support further exacerbate the complexities of managing change.

Employees may experience feelings of anxiety, ambiguity, and mistrust, resulting in decreased motivation, productivity, and job satisfaction. The present state highlights a critical gap between the potential of change management to drive employee performance and the reality of organizational change efforts that fall short of achieving desired outcomes.

The consequences of ineffective change management on employee performance are multifaceted and extend beyond the immediate challenges faced by individuals and organizations. Employees who feel disconnected or unsupported during periods of change may exhibit decreased morale, higher levels of stress, and increased absenteeism or turnover. This can lead to disruptions in workflow, reduced team cohesion, and diminished organizational resilience in the face of change. Moreover, the failure to effectively manage change erodes trust in leadership, undermines employee confidence in the organization's vision and direction, and compromises the overall effectiveness of change initiatives. At a macro level, the implications of poor change management practices may include missed opportunities for innovation, decreased competitiveness, and a loss of market relevance in an increasingly dynamic business landscape.

Addressing the effect of change management on employee performance requires a strategic focus on fostering a culture of transparency, right leadership style at the time, and training on new technology within organizations. It necessitates proactive leadership, comprehensive stakeholder engagement, and investment in employee development and support mechanisms. By aligning change management practices with organizational objectives and employee needs, organizations can unlock the full potential of their workforce, enhance employee performance, and position themselves for sustained success in an ever-evolving business environment. All these are issues capable of hampering the achievement of the short and long term goals of the organization and hence need to be swiftly addressed and dealt with accordingly. Therefore, it is as a result of these problems that this research seeks to examine the effect of change management on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State.

The broad objective of the study is to examine the effect of change management on employee performance in Juhel Pharmaceutical Company, Awka, Anambra State. The specific objectives are;

1. To ascertain the influence of leadership change on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State.
2. To determine the influence of change in organizational culture on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State.

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Change Management

Change involves the transformation or transition of something to a different state/condition, it is the act of becoming different or the result of being modified, when something is made different in a planned and unplanned way (Schnackenberg, Tomlinson, & Yu, 2019). Change refers to something new, the opposite of remaining in the same place or doing the same thing. According to Wanza & Nkuraru (2016), response to organizational change is carried out by stakeholders including customers and people working in the organization. These responses may be positive or negative, in form of acceptance or resistance respectively, depending on the available facts and how the people perceive effect of change as negative outlook can result in resistance. Wanza and Nkuraru (2016) emphasizes that change is a persistent element of an organization's life, at the functioning and planning or strategic level, because of its significance. Consequently, for a firm to succeed and remain viable in the constantly changing environment, that firm must be able to successfully

manage changes internally and externally. Though it appears there is no unanimity regarding the structure for organizational change management, but existing literature points to harmony among scholars and practitioners on two important issues. One, there is concurrence that change is being prompted by internal/or external factors, secondly, change occurs in many shapes, forms, and sizes. Change is a constant thing in the lifespan of an individual and the organization as a whole

Lewin defined change management as a process that includes creating a perception that change is required, then transforming toward favourable behaviour, and then maintaining that favourable behaviour so that it becomes a habit (Lewin, 1947). It is the implementation of process and instruments to manage the human resources side of change from the current situation to the desired one in a way that ensures the achievement of the results expected through that change (Hiatt & Creasy, 2012). Change management is defined as a holistic approach adopted in organizations to transform the organization from a particular situation to a desired one through structured coordination process with the stakeholders (Dalcher, 2019). On the other hand, change management can be defined as systematic approach by which managers can transform their organizations from a status to another in terms of appointing different goals, internal processes, and shared values.

Change management is also defined as a comprehensive approach that refers to preparing, directing, and supporting organization's employees and groups to achieve organizational change (Burke, 2017). Nwinyopugi (2018) defines change management as the continuous process of aligning an organization with its marketplace and doing it more responsively and effectively than competitors. Change management is branded by successful management of a business variation such that the managers, administrators, supervisors, and employers work effectively to implement and actualize the required method, using the necessary technology or organizational laid down process (Ilesanmi & Lasisi, 2015).

Leadership change

Leadership change is the ability to influence others through personal advocacy, vision and drive, and to access resources to build a solid platform for change (Higgs & Rowland, 2000). Change leadership is usually associated with a bigger vision and with the creation of a broader agency and urgency for change throughout the entire organization. The change leadership model motivates the members of the organization to be and lead the change, using collaborative, creative and motivational change approaches. Trainer (2021) pointed that, change leadership is strategic in nature. It sets the direction for change management. The first focus of a change leadership team is effective and purposeful communication disseminated much like any outreach initiative. Instead of a top-down approach, it is more effective for the team to focus on informing and educating the workforce, if it expects to diminish negative reactions.

Muia (2015) opined that, the long run relationship between leadership change and employee performance, co integration results show that leaders who want the best result should not only rely on a single leadership style. In other words, no leadership styles are preferred in any situation in an organization. Hence, a combination or mix leadership style can improve and maintain an organization's process and increases employee's commitment and increases in the job performance. Different leadership style and behaviour may affect the employee performance towards the tasks accomplishment and job performance (Vigoda-Gadot, 2007). Therefore, leadership style adopted by a leader is strongly related to Employees' job performance. The relationship between leadership change and employee performance state that employees with high quality relationship with their leader will practice a better job performance and satisfaction than those with low quality relationship (Davis & Holland 2002).

The study of Van Vianen, Kossek, and Liefvooghe, (2020) posits that employees who experienced a leadership change were less likely to trust their new leader, and this lack of trust was associated with lower job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The study also found that employees who had experienced a leadership change were more likely to perceive the leader's motives as being self-serving rather than beneficial to the organization. This lack of trust and decreased commitment can lead to decreased performance and productivity. One reason why leadership change can lead to decreased trust is that employees often have strong emotional bonds with their leaders and when a leadership change occurs, these emotional bonds are disrupted and employees may feel a sense of loss and uncertainty. This can make it difficult for employees to trust their new leader, as they may feel that the new leader does not understand them or their needs.

Change in Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is an organizational foundation containing norms, beliefs, and collective values that reflects the characteristic of an organization. It deals with how an employee behaves in the organization (Dwiarti & Wibowo, 2018). In other words, organizational culture refers to a noble value adhered to by all members of the organization and that distinguish an organization from others. A strong organizational culture tends to exhibit a condition where most employees perceive the same opinion related to the vision, mission, and organizational value. In contrast, a weak organizational culture could be seen from high variance in employees' opinion related to the organizational goal (Tecoalu, Suwandi, & Asri, 2022). Organizational culture is the shared values, beliefs, norms, and practices that shape the behavior of individuals within an organization (Schein, 2017). It provides a framework for understanding and responding to challenges and opportunities faced by the organization.

Organizations may seek to change their culture for various reasons, such as adapting to market changes, improving employee engagement, fostering innovation, or responding to external pressures. Change in organizational culture is often driven by the need for alignment between the current culture and the strategic goals of the organization (Cameron & Quinn, 2021). Changing organizational culture is a gradual and deliberate process that involves multiple stages. Kotter's eight-step model provides a framework for initiating and sustaining culture change (Kotter, 2014). The steps include creating a sense of urgency, building a guiding coalition, developing a vision and strategy, communicating the change vision, empowering employees, generating short-term wins, consolidating gains, and anchoring new approaches in the culture. Leadership plays a crucial role in driving culture change within an organization. Effective leaders act as change agents, setting the tone for the desired cultural shift, modelling the new behaviours, and providing a clear vision for the organization's future (Denison, 2018). Leadership commitment and consistency are key factors in successful culture change initiatives.

Resistance to change is a common challenge in organizational culture change efforts. Employees may resist new cultural norms and practices due to fear of the unknown, concerns about job security, or a perceived misalignment with personal values (Oreg, Vakola, & Armenakis, 2013). Recognizing and addressing resistance through communication, involvement, and support is essential for successful cultural transformation. Measuring the success of cultural change initiatives requires the use of appropriate metrics and assessments. Culture assessment tools, such as the Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI) developed by Cameron and Quinn (2019), can provide insights into the current and desired cultural profiles of an organization. Change in organizational culture is a strategic and ongoing process that requires careful planning, effective leadership, and a commitment to sustained efforts. By understanding the complexities involved and leveraging established

frameworks, organizations can navigate cultural change successfully and align their culture with their overarching goals and objectives.

Employee Performance

Performance could be narrowed down to either organizational performance or employee performance, albeit, they all are intertwined. However, the interest in this work is on employee performance. Performance in terms of effort extends to the job of an employee. According to Taghipour and Dejban (2013), employee performance is defined as the level of success of a person in performing tasks and achieving predetermined goals. Employee performance can be said to be successful and has been good if the person's desired objectives have been achieved properly. According to Ndulue and Ekechukwu (2016), the definition of employee performance is a function of the abilities and skills of individuals and businesses in certain situations. In the short term, the skills and abilities of employees tend to be more stable, whereas they are broadly more related to the work of employees.

Employee performance is measured in terms of how effective and efficient employees are in discharging their duties. This was the position of Donglin (2019) who states that employees' performance can be seen as how well employees in an organization execute their duties professionally. Nwafor and Baridam-Ngobe (2020) assert that it is the ability of an employee to accomplish his or her mission based on the expectations of an organization. It is the ability to create acceptable outcomes based on organizational plans.

The performance of employees is one construct that has generated a lot of interest in the organizational lexicon. Possibly because of the critical role it places in determining the overall performance of organizations, hence, the enormous interest in it. According to Ciner (2019), performance is how an employee fulfills his job duties and carries out the required tasks. Meanwhile, Ezeanyim, Uzuegbu and Igu (2019) stated that performance is a function of individuals' and businesses' abilities and skills in certain situations. In the short term, employees' skills and abilities are relatively stable. It is in a quantitative term, where the emphasis is laid on results such as profitability, return on investment and return on asset. However, the type of performance indicators to be used is determined by the form of the organization being studied. Key performance indicators for a manufacturing firm might be different from that of banks or high institutions.

Employee performance means how well an employee can perform on the job and assignments assigned to him measured against the generally accepted measure of performance standards set by the institutions. It is the product of the quality and quantity of work achieved by the employee in executing their duties in accordance with the tasks assigned to them (Nwafor & Baridam-Ngobe, 2020). When an employee meets an expectation or standard set according to an organization, then that employee is said to have performed well. However, their performance is influenced by a lot of things, their mindset is a critical part of those employee performance determinants.

Ayinde, Bolarinwa, Alarima, Kazeem and Kareem (2021) opined that the performance of employees is influenced by a lot of things including motivation, work environment and leadership in the agency. A key part of the workplace environment is the level of conflict and how they are handled. Bringing the importance of conflict to performance determination of employees to the fore is Olukayode (2015) who states that a well-managed conflict will improve the organizations by stimulating employee performance. On the other hand, Obasan (2011) stated that management is duty-bound to resolve conflicts properly for the sake of increasing employee performance. This is because when conflict is not properly managed, there cannot be a reasonable increase in employees' performance (Ayinde, Bolarinwa, Alarima, Kazeem and Kareem, 2021).

Empirical Review

Yohanis and Shashi (2023) conducted a study to assess the effect of Change Management on employee performance. The primary data for this study were collected from respondents randomly selected from employees. Descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation and percentage was used. Correlation analysis, regression and ANOVA were used as inferential statistics. Probability sampling was used with simple random technique to collect the desired responses. Result from correlation analysis used indicates that all four variables like Structural change; Technological change, Strategic change and leadership change are significantly affecting employee performance. Also, the researcher generalized that leadership change evaluation had strongest positive and statistically significant correlation with Employee Performance. As per the regression analysis technological change is the most dominating factor that influences the Change Management in the study area at most. Result of Multiple Regression revealed that technical change as a positive and statistically significant influential relationship (contribution) to Employee Performance with $\beta = 0.487$, at 95% confidence level ($p < 0.01$). But, structural change has a negative and significant influential relationship (contribution) to employee commitment with $\beta = -.422$, at 95% confidence level ($p < 0.01$). Therefore, it is recommended that the officials should give focus on structure change according to the study area.

Obialor (2023) conducted a study to examine the change management effect on employee performance of Comestar Manufacturing industry Onitsha, Anambra State. The population of the study was made up of 109 staff. The data was analysed using simple percentage, descriptive statistics, mean, standard deviation and correlation analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between leadership change, communication and technological change on employee performance. The conclusion was that change management had significant and positive effect on the employee performance of medium scale industry. Recommendation made include that, the change process organization design as a result of organization's orientation must motivate employees to want to participate, to choose to contribute, and enhance performance.

Zamanam (2021) studied the impact of change management on employees' performance through the modified role of organizational culture in Kuwaiti educational institutions Saudi Arabia. The study used technological change, cultural change, structural change, and human change as variables for change management, it was discovered that there is a significant impact of technological change, structural change, and human change on the employees' performance in Kuwaiti educational institutions. The research hypotheses were tested with Chi-square test statistic. Results showed that the structural creation of the institution and its management, departments, directorates, and units, evolving from the change in terms of workers' ideas, attitudes, habits in Kuwaiti educational institution. In light of the study results, the researcher recommends the following: The necessity for Kuwaiti educational institutions to integrate departments in a flexible manner, and to amend administrative units to enhance the employees' performance. And the need to pay attention to changing the directions of the future leadership, so that the management of Kuwaiti educational institutions adopts a new leadership style to confront the resistance to change among its workers.

Chuka and Umar (2021) aimed at evaluating the extent to which change management impacts on employee's performance in the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission Sector Abuja. The study adopted research design based on data collected through questionnaire survey distributed to staff of the Commission. Questionnaires were distributed electronically to 80 employees and 60 completed questionnaires were returned at a response rate of 75%. Non-probability sampling techniques were used. Using descriptive and inferential

statistics methods, this study found that a positive relationship existed between various changes in the Commission, the attitude of employees to work and their general performance. To the best knowledge of the researcher, few empirical studies have been conducted to determine how change management has impacted on employee performance in the Nigerian public sector; specifically, in the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission.

Udeme and Umar (2021) assessed the impact of change management on employee performance with evidence from Nile University of Nigeria Abuja. This study made use of a descriptive survey research design. Burke Litwin model of organizational change was adopted for this study because the model explains the linkages between variables and individual and organizational performance. The population consists of 1,400 staff (Academic and Non-Academic) staff of Nile University of Nigeria Abuja. Stratified random sampling techniques were employed to select the sample size of 311 from the population. Regression analysis was used to analyze the data that was collected using a five-point likert scale structured questionnaire. The results showed that organizational structure has a significance effect on the quality of employee service delivery in Nile University of Nigeria, there is a relationship between technological change and quality of employee service delivery in Nile University of Nigeria even though the relationship was not very strong. Leadership change significantly influences the quality of employee service delivery in Nile University of Nigeria. Human resource is an important internal strength of every organization and a source of competitive advantage, the study, therefore, recommended amongst others that organizations should communicate details of the change to the employees to minimize resistance.

Ochuko and Ayo-Balogun (2020) investigated the impact of organizational changes on employees' performance in union Bank Nigeria Plc. Lagos, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research designed method was adopted. Data were collected through a survey, using a structured questionnaire validated by experts. Three different branches of Union Bank Plc. Lagos, Nigeria were selected for the study and a sample size of 100 was determined using Taro Yamane techniques out of 134 total populations. The study used multinomial regression analytical model and applying Wald test statistic to tests the relationship between dependent and independent variables. The findings revealed that adopted measures of organizational changes were found to be statistically significant towards enhancing employees' performance of Nigeria bank, while technological and leadership changes are tools for measuring the effectiveness of organizational changes. The study therefore recommended that government should provide conducive environment for banks to enable them cope with any unexpected threat that may occur within the environment.

Meareg (2020) investigated the effect of organizational change in employee performance at dashen banks in head offices Ethiopia. The researcher adopted descriptive and explanatory research design with mixed research approach. Simple random sampling techniques were employed for this research with 269 sample size. Both primary and secondary data collection are applied with the main data collection instruments of questionnaire and observation. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis techniques were used to analysis the data. The finding of relationship results showed that there is a positive relationship between the organizational change dimension and employee performance at dashen bank. The study revealed that structural change, strategic change and technological change is not a significant determinant of employee performance. The researcher recommends that Manager must provide training for their employees for those resist change. So change can increase employee efficiency in their work activities to make satisfied employees and customer. The manager must create regular training program to update employees.

Kwizera, Olutayo, Irau, Wandiba, Patricia and Bayo (2019) conducted a study on the effect of organizational change on employee performance among selected commercial banks in Bujumbura, Burundi. The study adopted a cross-sectional design, the target population was 163 employees and the sample size was 116, however, only 104 successfully participated in the study. The main research instruments included questionnaires. The study revealed that structural change significantly affects employee performance by causing a variance of 56.8% ($R^2=0.568$, $P=0.000$). Furthermore, it was established that strategic change significantly affects employee performance by causing a variance of 47.2% ($R^2=0.472$, $P=0.000$). Lastly, the study revealed that technological change significantly affects employee performance by causing a variance of 51.4% ($R^2=0.514$, $p=0.000$). The study drew the conclusion that organizational change had a significant effect on employee performance. The study gave the following recommendations: the management of commercial banks should periodically change the way business is done in a manner that timely responds to the ever-dynamic customer demands. The management of commercial banks should practice appropriate strategic changes that enable them to offer services that meet the expectations of different groups of customers.

Mukhebi (2019), investigate the effects of change management on employee performance in commercial banks in Trans Nzoia County, Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Target population of the study consisted of 470 employees drawn from 14 commercial banks in Trans Nzoia County. A sample size of 216 of employee was arrived at and stratified simple random sampling used to categorize managers, supervisors/administrators and clerical /tellers. Data was collected using the questionnaires. Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Therefore, the study concluded that change management had significant effect on the employee performance in commercial banks in Trans Nzoia County. The study recommended that management of commercial banks undertaking organizational change should focus on participatory leadership and communication strategies to enhance employees' readiness for change.

Nwinyokpugi (2018), investigated organizational change management and employee's productivity in the Nigeria banking sector. A randomized population sample of 152 respondents which comprise employees and management staff of these banks were drawn using Taro Yamen sampling formula. The findings derived from the results presented in the analysis of the data indicates that all tested dimensions of organizational change management (change communication, change identification, employees' engagement, change implementation and incentives) are significantly associated with the measures of employee's productivity. It is specifically recommended that change communication should be systematic, change implementation should be initiated from the top management and down to the employees in a clear and consistent manner, and incentives should be based on organizational contractual policies.

Chiavoghi and Emerole (2017) examined the effects of change management on employee commitment, which leads to enhanced employee performance, in deposit money banks in Umuahia. The study indicated a significant positive effect by change management on commitment of employees. This study undertook a cross-sectional research survey consisting of 122 staff in ten (10) banks, made use of simple random sampling technique and Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient (ρ) for hypotheses testing, using Statistical Package for Social Sciences SPSS (20.0).

Wanza and Nkuraru (2016) investigated the Influence of change management on employee performance using a case of university of Eldoret, Kenya, the research considered a sample size of 121 employees using simple random sampling technique to select from a population of 403. Structured questionnaires and interview schedules were used to collect Primary data. Change management was proxied by technology, structure

leadership, and culture. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Multiple Regression analysis was used to analyze the data that was collected. Technology has a positive effect on employee performance. It was discovered in this study that employee performance was positively impacted by structural change, organizational leadership, technological change, and strong organizational culture. The study recommended that the university leadership needed to change their mindsets on the impact of change management, leadership styles that increase employee motivation to exceed expected results and a change process that is result oriented thus increasing their levels of employee's performance.

Olajide (2014) conducted a study that examines empirically change management and its effects on organizational performance of Nigerian telecoms industries. In conducting this study, a total of 300 staffs of Airtel were randomly selected from a staff population of 1000. Three hypotheses were advanced to guide the study and data collected for the study were analyzed using One-way Analysis of Variance. The result revealed that changes in technology has a significant effect on performance and that changes in customer taste has a significant effect on customer's patronage. The result also shows that changes in management via leadership has a significant effect on employee's performance. Based on the findings of the study, recommendation were made that telecoms industries in Nigeria should be pro-active to changes in such a competitive environment so as to experience smooth implementation of such changes. The study therefore concludes that nothing remain still in the world of business as change is the only thing that is constant.

Thomas (2014) considered Change management and its effects on organizational performance of Nigerian telecoms industries. The study covered telecommunication industry in Nigeria and depended on 300 staff of Airtel, Nigeria selected randomly. Questionnaire was used to collect data and descriptive statistics was used to analyze data with the help of scientific package for social sciences. It was discovered that change in management through leadership and change in technology have a significant effect on change management. It was recommended that management should be proactive in a competitive environment to ensure smooth implementation of change. The investigation provides observational holes on the need to cover more change management factors like communication.

Kinoti (2013) conducted research to evaluate the effects of change management on employee performance in Co-operative Bank of Kenya limited. The study used case study research design. In-depth interviews were conducted with interviewees who are head of key departments in Head office charged with change implementation. The presentation of findings was of qualitative form. The study found that the way in which a manager makes decisions, delegates" responsibility and interacts with employees could affect the entire organization. The study also found that embrace on technology had improved the organizations operations by offering a technology platform, which significantly improved employee performance. In addition, changes in organizational structures promote employee performance, due to effective supervisory relationships and work flow, which consequently influence productivity. Based on the findings the study recommended it is important for the management to embark on creating awareness on the new developments on how services and products are delivered among the targeted customers and orientation of the new technology and developments on employees.

Methodology

This research work adopted a survey research design because of the nature of the study. Survey research design is a type of design that allows researchers to collect data from sampled respondents about a phenomenon using a questionnaire, observation and or interviews.

In this study, the population of the study comprised of employees of Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambta State, Nigeria. Records from personnel department revealed that a total of 221 employees is identified across the organization selected for the study. Hence, the total population of the study was 221. The departments and Staff strength are

S/N	Department	Staff Strength
1	Production	27
2	Packaging	91
3	Quality Assurance Unit	14
4	Engineering	19
5	Human Resource	6
6	Account/Procurement/Finance	6
7	Internal Audit/Sales	3
8	Store	25
9	Security	17
10	Sanitation	13
Total		221

Source: Personnel Officer (2024).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample size is 142; Yaro yamane was used to reduce the population of 221 employees for easy distribution of questionnaire. All the items and element in a population has to be used. The population size was determined by Yaro Yamane statistical formula;

$$S = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;

N = Population

S = Sample Size

e = Error term (0.05)

1 = Constant

$$S = \frac{221}{1 + 221(0.05)^2}$$

$$S = \frac{221}{1 + 221(0.0025)}$$

$$S = \frac{221}{1 + 0.5525}$$

$$S = \frac{221}{1.5525}$$

S = 142

Sources of Data

The source of data for this study is majorly primary. Specifically, a structured questionnaire was used for this purpose.

Method of Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection is Questionnaire. Relevant data were collected through the use of five points Likert scale questionnaire which include; Strongly Agreed (5), Agreed (4), Disagreed (3), Strongly Disagreed (2), and, Undecided (1).

Reliability of Instrument

The reliability of instrument was obtained through Cronbach Alpha method through Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS version 25). 30 copies of the questionnaire were administered to respondents of Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited. The questionnaire was restructured and redistributed to the same respondents. Upon testing the reliability of responses to the items in the test instrument using correlation analysis a figure of 0.87 was obtained which shows that the instrument is very reliable. Below is the table reliability figure using Cronbach Alpha;

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.869	1.000	30

Cronbach Alpha (SPSS version 25)

Method of Data Analysis

Bio data collected were presented using simple mathematical tabular presentation based on frequency percentage. The data generated were analysed using Descriptive Statistics and hypotheses were tested using Multiple Linear Regression on Statistical packages for Social Science (version 25) at 5% level of significance.

Decision Rule:

Accept the Alternate hypothesis (H_a) if P -value is less than 0.05 (P -value < 0.05); otherwise accept the Null hypothesis (H_o).

Data Analysis

Questionnaire distribution and returns

One hundred and forty two questionnaires were distributed and one hundred and eleven was completed and returned, this represents 77%.

Data Analysis

The table below is the descriptive statistics that was computed to show the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values, statistics, etc.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
EPF	5	1.00	217.00	90.8000	91.28636
LDC	5	.00	210.00	86.6000	88.40701
OGC	5	1.00	222.00	88.8000	92.03641
Valid N (listwise)	5				

Interpretation

The descriptive statistics for the independent variables, employee performance (EPF), leadership changes (LDC), and organizational culture (OGC), were represented in Table 1. The mean is used to establish a baseline. The maximum and minimum numbers, on the other hand, aid in the detection of data problems. The variation from the mean is represented by the standard deviation. It is a risk indicator; the greater the standard deviation, the greater the risk. The standard deviation is a metric that expresses how much each item in a dataset deviates from the mean. It is the most reliable and extensively used metric. The standard deviations in the firms are 91.29, 88.41, and 92.04, for EPF, LDC, and OGC respectively.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	1.000 ^a	1.000	1.000	1.78331

a. Predictors: (Constant), TEC, LDC, OGC

Table 3: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	33329.620	3	11109.873	3493.461	.012 ^b
	Residual	3.180	1	3.180		
	Total	33332.800	4			

a. Dependent Variable: EPF

b. Predictors: (Constant), LDC, OGC

Table 4: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.190	1.232		1.778	.326
	LDC	2.122	.148	2.055	14.343	.044
	OGC	-.161	.186	-.163	-867	.545

a. Dependent Variable: EPF

In table 2, a regression analysis was conducted to test the leadership change, organizational culture and employee performance. Adjusted R squared is coefficient of determination which provides the distinction in the

dependent variable due to changes in the independent variables. From the findings in the table 2, the value of adjusted R squared shows a value of 0.100, showing that there was variation of 100% on employee performance due to changes in leadership change and organizational culture. This implies that all changes in employee performance could be accounted for by leadership change and organizational culture.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of leadership change on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State.

Table 4 reveals that the p-value is 0.044 shows that the hypothesis is statistically significant at level of significance (5%); hence p-value of the test statistic is less than alpha value ($0.044 < 0.05$).

In table 4, the regressed result shows that an evaluation of the leadership change of the explanatory variable shows positive statistically significant, hence coefficient value is 2.055 and t-statistics is 14.343, showing that leadership change is positively statistically significant on employee performance at 5% level of significance.

Decision:

Since p-value of the test statistic is less or equal to alpha, we therefore, reject null hypotheses and uphold alternative hypothesis which state that there is a significant influence of leadership change on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of change in organizational culture on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State.

Table 4 reveals that the p-value is 0.545 shows that the hypothesis is not statistically significant at level of significance (5%); hence p-value of the test statistic is greater than alpha value ($0.545 > 0.05$).

In table 4, the regressed result shows that an evaluation of the organizational culture on the explanatory variable shows negative statistically insignificant, hence coefficient value = -0.163 and t-statistics is -0.867, showing that organizational culture is negatively statistically insignificant on employee performance at 5% level of significance.

Decision:

Since p-value of the test statistic is less or equal to alpha, we therefore, reject alternate hypotheses and uphold null hypothesis which state that there is no significant relationship between organizational culture and employee performance in Juhel Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant in Awka, Anambra State.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one stated that there is a significant influence of leadership change on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State. This result is in line with Mukhebi (2019) that concluded that change management had significant effect on the employee performance in commercial banks in Trans Nzoia County. Chiavoghi and Emerole (2017) indicated a significant positive effect by change management on commitment of employees. Thomas (2014) discovered that change in management through leadership and change in technology have a significant effect on change management. Ochuko & Ayo-Balogun (2020) revealed that adopted measures of organizational changes were found to be statistically significant towards enhancing employees' performance of Nigeria bank,

Hypothesis two shows that there is no significant relationship between organizational culture and employee performance in Juhel Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant in Awka, Anambra State. This means that employees adhere to the norms and policies of the organization. Udeme and Umar (2021) showed that organizational

structure has a significance effect on the quality of employee service delivery in Nile University of Nigeria, Meareg (2020) results showed that there is a positive relationship between the organizational change dimension and employee performance at dashen bank. Kwizera ,Olutayo, Irau,Wandiba, Patricia& Bayo (2019) revealed that structural change significantly affects employee performance by causing a variance of 56.8% (R2= 0.568, P=0.000). Furthermore, it was established that strategic change significantly affects employee performance by causing a variance of 47.2% (R2= 0.472, P.0.000).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The broad objective of the study is to examine the effect of change management on employee performance in Juhel Pharmaceutical Company, Awka, Anambra State. Survey research design was applied. A sample of 142 was used from a population of 221. Data were generated from questionnaires administered to the respondents and analyzed, tested with multiples regression. From the results, there is a significant influence of leadership change on employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State. While there is no significant influence between change in organizational culture, technological change and employee performance in Juhel Parenteral Drug Limited, Awka, Anambra State. Meanwhile the overall multiples regression shows p-value of 0.012, hence, there is a significant influence between employee performance, leadership change, organizational culture and technological change. This implies that managing change effectively provide benefits that help organizations sustain competitive advantage in the changing world. This study therefore conclude that effective change management has contributed to the employee performance in Juhel Pharmaceutical Company, Awka, Anambra State

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were provided;

1. Leaders, as the key decision-makers, should determine the attainment, development, and disposition of organizational resources, thus motivate the members of the organization to be and lead the change.
2. There is need for the organizations to change their culture for various reasons, such as adapting to market changes, improving employee engagement, fostering innovation, or responding to external pressures.

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